

Kinetics of bromine addition to acrylic acid and methacrylic acid in aqueous solution

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Abstract : The most important feature of this potentiometric study of bromination of acrylic and methacrylic acids in aqueous medium is the complete solution of rate laws by varying $[Br^-]$ and $[H^+]$ over an extended concentration range. This observation completely rules out the possibilities of reactions of undissociated acid with Br_2 or Br_3^- and dissociated acid anion with Br_3^- for both acids. Values of rate constants and energy of activation were evaluated and interpreted. The reactivity of methacrylic acid was greater than that of acrylic acid. The enhancement of reactivity by methyl group depends on the nature of the substrate.

Keywords : Kinetics, bromine addition, acrylic acid, methacrylic acid, methyl effect, aqueous medium.

Introduction

A number of mechanisms have been proposed for the bromination of olefins¹⁻³. In presence of bromide ions, regarding electrophilic activity of the tribromide species controversy still persists⁴⁻¹². Electrophilic activity of the tribromide species was observed in unsaturated amides and esters¹³ and bromide assistance was found to be large with nitriles¹⁴. In continuation of bromination of unsaturated compounds, from deactivated to activated compounds, we report herein the kinetic results of bromination of acrylic (AAc) and methacrylic (MAAc) acids in aqueous medium in presence of bromide ions.

Results and discussion

The reaction is first order with respect to both substrate and bromine. The kinetic results show that the values of $k_2(K_c + [H^+])(1 + K[Br^-])$ remained constant for acrylic acid (Tables 2 to 6) and methacrylic acid (Tables

7 to 10) irrespective of variations in $[H^+]$'s and $[Br^-]$'s at all temperatures. This observation completely rules out bromination by undissociated acid with Br_2 and Br_3^- and dissociated acid with Br_3^- and to occur predominantly between acid anion and Br_2 species. This may be explained as follows. In our early work¹³ it was observed that the replacement of ethyl by methyl group in alkyl methacrylates decreases the rate of bromination by 0.7 times. Since the +I effect of -Me \gg -H, the rate of undissociated methacrylic acid may be predicted to be about $10^{-2} M^{-1} s^{-1}$ or even less. Due to ionization the rate of bromination increases by nearly 10^6 times, making the contribution of undissociated acid to the bromination insignificant as compared to that of acid anion. Also in the case of the anion, due to repulsion between like charges, there is negligible contribution to the reaction rate by Br_3^- species and is not observed in this highly reactive acid anion. Of the two title compounds studied, the activation energy, E_a for the methyl substituted one was found to be 4 kcal mol⁻¹ less than that for the other. (E_a (AAc) = 14.4 kcal mol⁻¹ and E_a (MAAc) = 10.4 kcal mol⁻¹). This is due to the cumulative effect of the two activating groups -COO⁻ and -Me (both +I groups) in increasing the electron density at the olefinic linkage greatly and accordingly a 500-fold difference in the rate was observed (Table 11). However, the difference in the

Table 1. Dissociation constants k_c and K at different temperatures

Temp. (°C)	K	$k_c \times 10^5 (M)$	
		AAc	MAAc
30	15.89	6.607	4.169
38	14.18	6.457	4.074
46	14.03	6.310	3.981
54	13.24	6.166	3.890

Table 2. Rate constants at various $[H^+]$ and $[Br^-]$ for acrylic acid-bromine reaction

$[AAc]_0 = 1.252 \times 10^{-3} M$, $[Br_2]_0 = 1 \times 10^{-4} M$, $I = 0.5 M$, $A = k_2 (L \text{ mol}^{-1} \text{ s}^{-1})$, $B = k_2(K_c + [H^+])(1 + K [Br^-]) \times 10^2$,
Temp. = 30 °C

$[Br^-] = [H^+]$ (M)	0.05 M		0.10 M		0.15 M		0.20 M		0.25 M	
	A	B	A	B	A	B	A	B	A	B
0.0010	94.26	18.03	65.98	18.21	52.21	18.40	43.11	19.20	35.65	18.90
0.0025	40.70	18.74	27.93	18.55	21.44	18.62	18.22	19.54	15.84	20.22
0.0050	21.40	19.45	14.70	19.29	11.94	20.47	9.72	20.57	8.17	20.58
0.0075	13.79	18.72	10.08	19.75	7.67	19.65	6.61	20.88	5.30	19.92
0.0100	11.10	20.05	7.58	19.74	5.87	20.00	5.13	21.56	4.08	20.44
0.0125	8.67	19.54	5.91	19.21	4.86	20.65	3.65	19.16	3.22	20.11

Table 3. Rate constants at various $[H^+]$ and $[Br^-]$ for acrylic acid-bromine reaction

$[AAc]_0 = 1.252 \times 10^{-3} M$, $[Br_2]_0 = 1 \times 10^{-4} M$, $I = 0.5 M$, $A = k_2 (L \text{ mol}^{-1} \text{ s}^{-1})$, $B = k_2(K_c + [H^+])(1 + K [Br^-]) \times 10^2$,
Temp. = 38 °C

$[Br^-] = [H^+]$ (M)	0.05 M		0.10 M		0.15 M		0.20 M		0.25 M	
	A	B	A	B	A	B	A	B	A	B
0.0025	88.68	39.58	58.36	37.13	48.63	40.18	39.49	40.12	33.64	40.57
0.0050	42.72	37.66	29.02	36.47	23.69	38.65	21.16	42.46	16.91	40.28
0.0075	28.65	37.72	20.11	37.73	15.92	38.79	14.32	42.93	11.69	41.58
0.0100	22.40	39.24	14.78	36.90	12.73	41.28	9.88	39.39	8.87	42.00
0.0125	18.98	41.50	12.41	38.67	10.18	41.20	7.96	39.62	6.88	40.65
0.0150	14.56	38.18	10.35	38.67	8.23	39.95	7.19	42.90	5.97	42.28

Table 4. Rate constants at various $[H^+]$ and $[Br^-]$ for acrylic acid-bromine reaction

$[AAc]_0 = 1.252 \times 10^{-3} M$, $[Br_2]_0 = 1 \times 10^{-4} M$, $I = 0.5 M$, $A = k_2 (L \text{ mol}^{-1} \text{ s}^{-1})$, $B = k_2(K_c + [H^+])(1 + K [Br^-]) \times 10^2$,
Temp. = 46 °C

$[Br^-] = [H^+]$ (M)	0.05 M		0.10 M		0.15 M		0.20 M		0.25 M	
	A	B	A	B	A	B	A	B	A	B
0.0025	142.48	62.14	103.08	63.49	81.47	64.82	68.24	66.57	58.19	67.23
0.0050	71.38	61.49	51.06	62.12	39.07	61.41	34.91	67.27	28.13	64.19
0.0075	49.82	64.12	35.88	65.22	25.92	60.86	22.59	65.03	19.82	67.56
0.0100	36.63	62.72	28.05	67.83	21.16	66.11	17.85	68.35	15.61	70.82
0.0125	32.48	60.43	20.64	62.31	16.07	62.68	13.84	66.18	12.28	69.57
0.0150	26.44	67.76	18.43	66.70	13.01	61.23	11.43	65.51	10.11	68.64

Table 5. Rate constants at various $[H^+]$ and $[Br^-]$ for acrylic acid-bromine reaction

$[AAc]_0 = 1.252 \times 10^{-3} M$, $[Br_2]_0 = 1 \times 10^{-4} M$, $I = 0.5 M$, $A = k_2 (L \text{ mol}^{-1} \text{ s}^{-1})$, $B = k_2(K_c + [H^+])(1 + K [Br^-]) \times 10^2$,
Temp. = 54 °C

$[Br^-] = [H^+]$ (M)	0.05 M		0.10 M		0.15 M		0.20 M		0.25 M	
	A	B	A	B	A	B	A	B	A	B
0.0025	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	110.04	121.5
0.0050	128.62	108.2	90.83	106.8	71.78	108.5	63.58	117.4	53.67	117.1
0.0075	84.77	106.5	63.19	111.0	50.20	113.3	40.07	110.5	35.93	117.1
0.0100	64.34	107.6	45.41	106.3	37.52	112.7	31.36	115.1	27.82	120.6
0.0125	49.47	103.3	36.82	107.5	29.59	111.0	25.07	114.9	22.24	120.4
0.0150	42.63	106.7	31.79	111.3	24.51	110.2	22.13	121.6	18.58	120.6

Table 6. Rate constants at various $[\text{Br}^-]$ and temperatures for acrylic acid-bromine reaction

 $[\text{AAc}]_0 = 1.252 \times 10^{-3} \text{ M}$, $[\text{Br}_2]_0 = 1 \times 10^{-4} \text{ M}$, $I = 0.5 \text{ M}$, $C = \text{mean value of } k_2(K_c + [\text{H}^+])(1 + K[\text{Br}^-])$ obtained for different $[\text{H}^+]$ at a particular $[\text{Br}^-]$, $D = C \times 10^{-3}/K_c$

Temp. ($^{\circ}\text{C}$)	30		38		46		54	
	C	D	C	D	C	D	C	D
0.05	0.19 ± 0.01	2.89	0.39 ± 0.02	6.04	0.65 ± 0.04	10.24	1.06 ± 0.03	17.27
0.10	0.19 ± 0.01	2.90	0.38 ± 0.01	5.82	0.65 ± 0.03	10.24	1.09 ± 0.02	17.61
0.15	0.20 ± 0.01	2.97	0.40 ± 0.01	6.20	0.63 ± 0.02	9.96	1.11 ± 0.02	18.03
0.20	0.20 ± 0.01	3.05	0.41 ± 0.02	6.39	0.66 ± 0.02	10.54	1.16 ± 0.04	18.80
0.25	0.20 ± 0.01	3.04	0.41 ± 0.01	6.39	0.68 ± 0.04	10.78	1.19 ± 0.02	19.33

Table 7. Rate constants at various $[\text{H}^+]$ and $[\text{Br}^-]$ for methacrylic acid-bromine reaction

 $[\text{MAAc}]_0 = 1 \times 10^{-3} \text{ M}$, $[\text{Br}_2]_0 = 1 \times 10^{-3} \text{ M}$, $I = 0.5 \text{ M}$, $A = k_2 (\text{L mol}^{-1} \text{ s}^{-1})$, $B = k_2(K_c + [\text{H}^+])(1 + K[\text{Br}^-])$, Temp. = $30 \text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$

$[\text{Br}^-] = [\text{H}^+]$ (M)	0.10 M		0.15 M		0.20 M		0.25 M		0.30 M	
	A	B								
0.100	242.00	62.68	198.83	67.30	156.52	65.42	121.37	60.37	-	-
0.125	206.98	67.00	147.79	62.53	118.65	61.99	97.63	60.70	86.45	62.34
0.150	169.60	65.88	126.01	63.97	98.52	61.76	82.52	61.57	70.46	60.96
0.175	143.70	65.12	113.12	67.00	84.40	61.72	72.98	63.52	61.30	61.80
0.200	130.10	67.38	97.06	65.69	74.08	61.91	61.92	61.59	57.59	66.44
0.225	114.91	66.95	80.52	61.31	69.97	65.78	56.46	63.18	-	-

Table 8. Rate constants at various $[\text{H}^+]$ and $[\text{Br}^-]$ for methacrylic acid-bromine reaction

 $[\text{MAAc}]_0 = 1 \times 10^{-3} \text{ M}$, $[\text{Br}_2]_0 = 1 \times 10^{-3} \text{ M}$, $I = 0.5 \text{ M}$, $A = k_2 (\text{L mol}^{-1} \text{ s}^{-1})$, $B = k_2(K_c + [\text{H}^+])(1 + K[\text{Br}^-])$, Temp. = $38 \text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$

$[\text{Br}^-] = [\text{H}^+]$ (M)	0.10 M		0.15 M		0.20 M		0.25 M		0.30 M	
	A	B								
0.100	380.97	94.56	284.38	91.65	243.30	96.43	195.51	91.98	166.53	90.68
0.125	298.60	92.63	238.88	96.23	186.63	92.43	159.48	93.77	134.85	91.78
0.150	250.82	93.37	199.07	96.22	167.07	99.32	137.45	96.98	121.31	99.07
0.175	211.51	91.85	166.53	93.91	139.35	96.64	111.98	92.17	101.14	96.36
0.200	189.11	93.86	153.79	99.10	112.91	89.49	99.53	93.63	90.20	98.21
0.225	160.78	89.77	134.37	97.57	110.01	98.09	92.12	97.49	-	-

Table 9. Rate constants at various $[\text{H}^+]$ and $[\text{Br}^-]$ for methacrylic acid-bromine reaction

 $[\text{MAAc}]_0 = 1 \times 10^{-3} \text{ M}$, $[\text{Br}_2]_0 = 1 \times 10^{-3} \text{ M}$, $I = 0.5 \text{ M}$, $A = k_2 (\text{L mol}^{-1} \text{ s}^{-1})$, $B = k_2(K_c + [\text{H}^+])(1 + K[\text{Br}^-])$, Temp. = $46 \text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$

$[\text{Br}^-] = [\text{H}^+]$ (M)	0.10 M		0.15 M		0.20 M		0.25 M		0.30 M	
	A	B								
0.100	563.46	135.45	447.08	138.85	342.96	130.60	295.34	133.18	255.47	133.13
0.125	444.34	133.51	336.42	130.60	279.24	132.89	234.77	132.32	202.52	131.91
0.150	396.98	143.13	289.25	134.73	248.31	141.80	201.54	136.30	182.80	142.87
0.175	321.24	135.12	256.87	139.59	210.60	140.30	174.67	137.81	153.65	140.10
0.200	285.83	137.40	218.34	135.59	183.87	140.00	148.31	133.73	135.52	141.21
0.225	249.53	134.93	190.35	132.99	158.33	135.62	141.01	143.04	-	-

rate of bromination between acrylate and crotonate ions was reported to be only 35-fold¹⁵. These observations thus explain the fact that the two activating groups, $-\text{COO}$

and $-\text{Me}$, when placed at the same carbon atom have greater effect on the electrophilic addition than when placed at different carbon atoms of the reaction site.

Table 10. Rate constants at various $[H^+]$ and $[Br^-]$ for methacrylic acid-bromine reaction

$[MAAc]_0 = 1 \times 10^{-3} M$, $[Br_2]_0 = 1 \times 10^{-3} M$, $I = 0.5 M$, $A = k_2 (L \text{ mol}^{-1} \text{ s}^{-1})$, $B = k_2(K_c + [H^+])(1 + K [Br^-])$, Temp. = 54 °C

$[Br^-] = [H^+]$	0.10 M		0.15 M		0.20 M		0.25 M		0.30 M	
(M)	A	B	A	B	A	B	A	B	A	B
0.100	-	-	689.71	206.03	568.00	207.29	511.20	220.41	414.17	206.01
0.125	736.86	214.12	552.22	206.18	449.02	204.80	388.13	209.17	342.47	212.91
0.150	639.00	222.81	469.22	210.22	397.60	217.62	327.69	211.91	288.58	215.28
0.175	539.00	219.50	405.71	212.05	332.23	212.14	284.00	214.25	251.73	219.08
0.200	459.80	213.76	342.47	204.56	291.28	212.56	261.58	225.92	225.91	224.69
0.225	428.33	224.01	316.46	212.65	267.29	219.43	216.74	210.22	-	-

Table 11. Second order rate constants (k'_{Br_2}) at different temperatures

Temp. (°C)	AAc $10^{-3} k'_{Br_2}$	MAAc $10^{-6} k'_{Br_2}$
30	2.97 ± 0.08	1.53 ± 0.05
38	6.17 ± 0.22	2.32 ± 0.05
46	10.35 ± 0.43	3.43 ± 0.03
54	18.21 ± 1.10	5.31 ± 0.09

The relative reactivities of pairs of compounds differing only by a -Me group at the olefinic carbon, vary widely depending on the nature of the substituent already present. A comparison of relative rates of bromination in aqueous medium for such pairs of compounds having substituents ranging from highly deactivating -CN group (-I) on the one hand^{13,14} and highly activating -COO⁻ group (+I) on the other shows clearly that the accelerating effect of the methyl group to the reaction rate is far less with -CN group than with -COO⁻ group. The methyl effect in the case of other intermediate pairs, such as acrylamide and methacrylamide and alkyl acrylates and alkyl methacrylates was found to be in between the two extreme cases (Table 12). Thus a methyl substituent in acid anion causes a large decrease in E_a (4 kcal mol⁻¹) with 500-fold rate increase compared to amides and esters where the decrease in E_a is about 1.5 kcal mol⁻¹ with 24- to 55-fold rate increase. Because of the powerful deactivating group in nitriles the electron accession of the methyl group is not fully felt at the double bond and hence the magnitude of decrease in E_a is only very small (0.3 kcal mol⁻¹) with a 2-fold increase in the rate.

It was observed that $k_{Br_2}/k_{Br_3^-}$ varied regularly in a set of compounds. The ratio increased with the increasing order of the reactivity of the substrate^{13,14}. It was found that the contribution by $k_{Br_3^-}$ is negligible in the case of

the most reactive methacrylate anion and the contribution by k_{Br_2} is negligible in the least reactive acrylonitrile. The order of reactivity is AAc anion > acrylamide (AAM) > ethyl acrylate (EA) > methyl acrylate (MA) > acrylonitrile (AN) and for methyl substituted compounds it is MAAc anion > methacrylamide (MAAM) > ethyl methacrylate (EMA) > methyl methacrylate (MMA) > methacrylonitrile (MAN) and the respective observed $k_{Br_2}/k_{Br_3^-}$ follows the same trend.

The products formed in the bromination of the title compounds studied in aqueous medium were dibromide and bromohydrin; their ratios at different bromide concentrations were determined by estimating the amount of bromohydrin by employing a standard procedure¹³. The product ratio values of [bromohydrin]/[dibromide] at various $[Br^-]$'s for bromination of AAc and MAAc in aqueous medium at 30 °C are given in Table 13. In this Table 13 are also included the corresponding product ratio values for the compounds AAM, MAAM, MA and MMA for comparison¹³. In conclusion, the fact that the bromohydrin to dibromide ratio is large in the case of acrylic and methacrylic acids compared to that obtained for esters and amides strongly suggests that there is an easy approach for the neutral water molecules than for the like charged Br⁻ and Br₃⁻ species towards the bromonium ion intermediates formed by acid anions during the course of the reaction.

Experimental

Materials and methods :

Acrylic and methacrylic acids (BDH, LR) were dried over anhydrous sodium sulphate and distilled twice under reduced pressure in an atmosphere of pure dry nitrogen. Sodium bromide (LR Sarabai Chemicals) was thrice re-

Table 12. A comparison of relative rates and E_a for bromination in aqueous medium

Substrate	k'_{Br_2} ($M s^{-1}$)	k_{Me}/k_H	E_a ($kcal mol^{-1}$)	E_{Me}/E_H	Ref.
AAc anion	2.97×10^3	-	14.4	-	Present work
MAAc anion	1.53×10^6	515.2	10.4	4.0	"
MA	0.12	-	14.8	-	13
MMA	5.80	48.3	13.1	1.7	"
EA	0.17	-	14.4	-	"
EMA	9.30	54.7	12.8	1.6	"
AAm	1.67	-	14.4	-	"
MAAm	47.00	28.1	13.0	1.4	"
AN (k_{Br_3})	0.58×10^{-3}	-	17.9	-	14
MAN	1.21×10^{-3}	2.09	17.0	0.9	"

Table 13. The values of [bromohydrin]/[dibromide] at various $[Br^-]$

$[Br^-]$ (M)	AAc	MAAc	AAm	MAAm	MA	MMA
0.10	9.57	8.79	4.2	3.88	2.59	1.19
0.15	6.89	5.35	-	2.54	-	-
0.20	6.08	4.78	1.74	2.07	1.04	0.57
0.25	4.97	4.30	-	1.75	-	-
0.30	4.07	3.24	1.25	-	0.83	0.32

crystallized from distilled water and the hydrated crystals were dehydrated first in an air oven at 130 °C and then in a vacuum desiccator over sodium hydroxide. Guaranteed samples of sodium nitrate, perchloric acid and bromine were used as such.

All the kinetic experiments were carried out by the potentiometric method using Pt, Br_2/Br^- and glass electrodes fitted into a specially fabricated reaction vessel.

The concentration of the substrate was of the order of $1.2 \times 10^{-3} M$ and the initial bromine concentration $[Br_2]_0$ at $1.0 \times 10^{-3} M$. The concentration of bromide was varied from 0.05 to 0.3 M . The concentration of perchloric acid was varied from 1.00×10^{-3} to $1.25 \times 10^{-2} M$ for acrylic acid and 0.1 to 0.225 M for methacrylic acid. Sodium nitrate was added to maintain ionic strength ($\mu = 0.5 M$). The reactions were conducted at 30, 38, 46, 54 °C. At each temperature, kinetic runs were carried out at different concentrations of perchloric acid for each bromide concentration.

As the substrate concentration was present in large excess in all the kinetic runs, the observed potential (E) was found to fall linearly with time indicating the unior order in bromine. The values of pseudo-first order rate constant (k_1) were obtained from the relation⁶,

$$K_1 = -(dE/dt) \times 2F/RT \quad (1)$$

where F and R have the usual significances. dE/dt values in mV/s were obtained from the plots of E versus time. The observed overall second-order rate constant, k_2 , was obtained by dividing k_1 by the initial concentration of the substrate. Due to ionization, both acid anion as well as undissociated acid may react with the brominating species, Br_2 and Br_3^- . Hence in the case of bromination of olefinic acids in presence of bromide ions, there are two reactive olefinic species, the neutral acid molecule and its anion and two likely brominating agents, molecular bromine and tribromide ion. The reaction scheme is

The values of k_2 were separated into k_{Br_2} , $k_{Br_3^-}$, k'_{Br_2} and $k'_{Br_3^-}$, the second-order rate constants corresponding to the reactions of the undissociated acids and acid anions with Br_2 and Br_3^- species using the equation⁶,

$$\begin{aligned} (K_c + [H^+])(1 + K [Br^-]) &= (k_{Br_2} + k_{Br_3^-} \\ K [Br^-] [H^+] + K_c (k'_{Br_2} + k'_{Br_3^-} K [Br^-]) & \quad (2) \end{aligned}$$

The values of tribromide formation constant, K , at vari-

ous temperatures were derived from the relationship,

$$\log K = 325.1/T + 0.1281 \quad (3)$$

obtained by using the K values of Scaife and Tyrrell¹⁵. The dissociation constants of these acids, K_c at $\mu = 0.5$ M used in eq. (2), were determined at 30, 38, 46 and 54 °C by pH titration method (Table 1).

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